

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

UKRAINE'S ROLE IN THE NEW FORMAT OF GLOBAL ECONOMIC STABILITY

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JEL: F01, O13, O33, O57, Q01

Abstract

The article analyses the factors that may lead to the transition of the world community to an era of greater stability and predictability of development. We examine trends in demography, technology, economics and geopolitics that create the preconditions for sustainable progress and conflict reduction in the long term. We believe that future stability will be based on the territory of the breadbasket, with no need for new territory as the population will not grow. Also, artificial intelligence can be used to develop new materials, energy sources, and resource-saving technologies that will contribute to sustainable development. The article analyses the factors that can lead the world community to an era of greater stability and predictability of development. It examines trends in demography, technology, economics and geopolitics that create the preconditions for sustainable progress and conflict reduction in the long term. Overall, the article offers an optimistic view of the future, where sustainability and predictability of development can become a reality thanks to technological advances, demographic trends and geopolitical changes.

Keywords: stability, sustainable development, demography, technology, economy, agriculture

In recent decades, the world has experienced many upheavals - wars, revolutions, economic crises, pandemics. However, there are strong arguments that global development will become more stable and predictable in the future. Let's look at the main factors that can lead to such stability.

1. The idea that the global economy depends solely on the world's 500 largest cities

The idea that the global economy is solely dependent on the world's 500 largest cities is an overly simplistic view. According to a study by the Brookings Institution, these 500 cities generate only about 50% of global GDP, which is \$30 trillion out of \$85 trillion of total global (GDP Brookings Institution, 2022). In fact, economic activity extends far beyond these cities to smaller towns, rural areas, and remote regions. For example, agriculture contributes about \$3 trillion to global GDP per year, and it is concentrated in rural areas (World Bank, 2021). More than 50% of the world's population lives in rural areas (World Bank, 2022). The contribution of industrial production to global GDP is estimated at \$25 trillion (World Bank, 2022). Most production capacities are not located in large cities, but in industrial centres and enterprises in small and medium-sized towns. The service sector (trade, transport, tourism, IT, etc.) generates more than 50% of global GDP. Thanks to outsourcing and remote work, many companies are successfully operating outside of large cities. Therefore, focusing on just the 500 largest cities does not reflect the complexity of the global economy, which includes interconnected

processes in different regions and sectors around the world. This suggests that the global economy is becoming an increasingly resilient and balanced system, less dependent on individual centres. Therefore, we can expect greater economic stability in the future. Big cities are indeed centres of population concentration and consumption, but they do not create added value by themselves. Growth occurs where goods and services are created. Most goods are not produced in megacities, but in industrial centres, factories and plants located outside of large cities. The same goes for agriculture, mining, etc. IT companies and startups can operate successfully from anywhere in the world thanks to remote work and outsourcing. Geographical location is becoming less important. Financial and business services are also increasingly provided virtually, without being tied to metropolitan cities. As a result, economic activity is spreading far beyond the borders of large cities. Rural areas, small towns and remote areas also make a major contribution to the economy. The world is becoming more and more globally connected, and location has less and less of an impact on business opportunities and value creation. Therefore, it is wrong to limit the economy to big cities. The development of infrastructure and logistics allows companies to operate efficiently even in remote regions. The construction of roads, bridges, railways, airports, and seaports makes it easier to transport inputs and finished goods. The spread of high-speed internet opens up opportunities for online business development, freelancing and outsourcing anywhere in

the world. Geography is no longer an obstacle. The growth of the middle class in developing countries is opening up new markets and business opportunities outside of traditional economic centres. The emergence of new financial technologies - cryptocurrencies, blockchain, fintech, etc. - is reducing dependence on traditional financial institutions in large cities. The development of local production infrastructure and clusters in small towns and rural areas is also contributing to economic growth outside of metropolitan areas.

2. The theory that corporations will replace states

The COVID-19 pandemic has clearly demonstrated that it is national governments that determine restriction and quarantine policies. Corporations have been forced to comply with these decisions. Even the largest global companies are registered and operate within the jurisdiction of specific countries. They cannot ignore national legislation. Governments control key infrastructure such as roads, bridges, ports, and energy grids. Without it, no corporation can operate. Governments set and collect taxes and restrict capital flows. Corporations do not have such opportunities and are dependent on government decisions. Citizens see themselves as part of nations, not as consumers of specific companies. This forms their identity and loyalty. In times of crisis, national unity is strengthened. We saw this during COVID and now in Ukraine. Corporate brands cannot compete with this. Military conflicts, such as in Palestine, demonstrate the monopoly of states on military force. Corporations do not have an army or intelligence. Only states can conduct full-scale hostilities. States determine the legitimacy of certain military formations. Groups that Israel and the United States consider terrorist are legitimate armed forces for Palestine. Even a powerful corporation cannot effectively counteract economic sanctions imposed by a state against another state, such as the United States against Iran. Only states officially recognise borders and statehood. Corporations are forced to take into account the geopolitical realities and interests of the countries where they operate. Civic identity has a much stronger impact on people's behaviour than brand loyalty. Patriotism often outweighs business interests.

3. The period of human growth is coming to an end, and at the same time, we are approaching the point of technology singularity

Global population growth is indeed slowing down. According to the United Nations, the average annual population growth rate has decreased from 2.1% in 1965-1970 to 1.1% in 2020-2025 (United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division, 2022). It is expected that by 2100 the population will reach about 10.9 billion people and stabilise (United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division, 2022). This is accompanied by technological progress, including the development of artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things, cloud computing, and blockchain. The ranking of the world's most expensive companies in 2000 was dominated by industrial giants: General Electric,

Citigroup, Exxon Mobil (Fortune, 2000). But in 2022, technology companies are leading the way: Apple, Microsoft, Alphabet (Google), Amazon, Meta (Facebook) (CompaniesMarketCap, 2023). "Smart cities" using AI, sensors, and cloud computing will help to use resources more efficiently to maintain a stable population. Autonomous cars, drone delivery, virtual and augmented reality will partially compensate for the slowdown in physical space growth. Localised production will reduce the need for transport and logistics.

4. While the world is concerned about the struggle for leadership between the United States and China, small and medium-sized countries have a chance to build their own competitive advantages by specialising in certain links in global value chains.

Given the limited leverage, the attempts of small countries like Ukraine, Taiwan or Slovakia to change the global balance of power are rather futile (Yevropeiska Pravda, 2023). For countries of Ukraine's size, the struggle to change the world's bipolarity or multipolarity is a waste of effort. Instead, these countries can focus on using existing opportunities to build their own competitive advantages. Namely, by embedding themselves in certain links of global value chains. For example, Taiwan has successfully specialised in semiconductor manufacturing, Slovakia in the automotive industry, and Estonia in e-government and digital services. Ukraine also has prospects for finding its niche in both traditional sectors (agricultural production, mechanical engineering) and innovative ones (IT outsourcing, high-tech, biotechnology, etc.) Ukraine has a strong human capital in IT, engineering, and science, which is the basis for the development of high-tech industries. Ukrainian IT specialists are already in demand for outsourcing around the world. Ukraine's agrarian and industrial potential also opens up broad prospects for participation in global value chains, from food supply to component manufacturing (Ukrayinska Pravda, 2020) (Industry4Ukraine, 2022). Ukraine's favourable geographical location allows it to develop transport infrastructure, logistics and distribution hubs between Europe and Asia. That is, instead of fighting in vain for a global redistribution of power, small states should pragmatically use the opportunities available to deepen their own specialisation in the international division of labour. This is what will guarantee their economic success.

5. The idea and benefits of globalisation have lost out to localisation. The battle continues.

Globalisation, as a concept of integration of economies and cultures on a global scale, was until recently considered to be a development trend with no alternative. However, recently there has been a certain disillusionment with globalisation and a rise in supporters of localisation. This is due to the following factors:

- The financial crisis of 2008 demonstrated the vulnerability of the global financial system due to the interconnectedness and dominance of TNCs (Wikiwand, 2022) (Wikipedia, 2022).

- The COVID-19 pandemic has exposed the weaknesses of extended intercontinental supply chains and the dependence of countries on imports of strategic goods (Radio Svoboda, 2021).

- Increasing threats of cyberattacks on critical infrastructure facilities due to their integration into global networks (Hromovenko K.V., 2021).

- The outbreak of the migration crisis in 2015 led to a rethinking of open borders as a consequence of globalisation (ZN UA, 2022).

Instead, the concept of localisation, which implies a certain degree of self-isolation and autarky of individual countries or regions, has received a new lease of life. In particular, the United States is implementing a reshoring policy - the return of industrial production from Asia to the United States. In Ukraine, after 2014, with the outbreak of the war in the east of the country, import substitution for certain goods and services has also been introduced (Prozorro, 2022). During the pandemic, both countries faced a shortage of critical medical products due to their foreign production, which led to an adjustment of strategies towards localisation.

Taking all these factors into account, we believe future stability will be based on:

1. The territories are agricultural, no new population is needed. The population will not grow.

The areas under cultivation will not need to be expanded as population growth slows. Innovations in agriculture, such as precision farming, hydroponics, vertical farms, and GMO crops, will increase yields. Smart monitoring systems will optimise the use of fertilisers, water and soil. The development of biotechnology will create alternatives to traditional food products with a lower impact on the ecosystem. Reducing losses from food shortages and spoilage will also make it possible to feed a stable number of people more efficiently. The development of agricultural technologies will significantly reduce the use of pesticides and fertilisers through precision farming that takes into account the characteristics of each field. This will improve the environmental friendliness of agriculture. Reducing food waste and losses will also have a positive effect on the environment. A stable population will mean a steady demand for food and predictability for the agricultural sector.

2. Material production will not grow, but will even fall due to efficiency

Material production volumes will stabilise as demand for most goods stops growing in line with the population. The spread of automation, robotics, the Internet of Things, 3D printing, and artificial intelligence will increase labour productivity and allow the same amount of output to be produced with fewer resources. The use of modern materials and resource-efficient technologies will also reduce consumption. Circular economy and sharing models will reduce the demand for new things. The spread of the closed-loop economy model will promote the reuse of materials and recycling of resources. This will reduce the need to extract new raw materials. Smart design and recycling of products will extend their useful life. The growth of the service economy will also reduce material intensity.

3. After a period of hot wars and economic wars, the hegemony of some countries and ideas will be established and there will be no more pressure, either economic or socio-political, for a new round of transformation.

At the end of the period of geopolitical turbulence, the great powers will build a new balance of power and spheres of influence. Global institutions will also adapt to new realities and ensure stability. Leading technological, economic, and humanitarian ideas will find consensus and become the foundation for further development. Societies will reach a certain "saturation" in their economic and political aspirations. This will eliminate the preconditions for new shocks and conflicts, at least for a while. Improvements in the system of global governance and multilateral institutions will strengthen international cooperation in addressing common problems of humanity. Harmonisation of technical standards will facilitate trade and economic relations. Promoting the values of sustainable development and responsibility will inspire confidence in the future.

Conclusions. The article describes how, after a period of geopolitical turbulence, the great powers will build a new balance of power and spheres of influence, and global institutions will adapt to the new realities and ensure stability. Leading technological, economic and humanitarian ideas will find consensus and become the foundation for further development. Overall, the article offers an optimistic view of the future, where sustainability and predictability of development can become a reality thanks to technological advances, demographic trends and geopolitical changes.

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